

Job Satisfaction Among Nurses

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ABSTRACT

Job satisfaction is “the one’s feeling toward his/ her job. In which intrinsic and extrinsic factors influence job satisfaction”. Intrinsic factors are an internal willingness to perform duty with satisfaction and internal motives. External factor is the organization provides fridge benefits to the committed professional. Nursing is the most gratifying, demanding and emotionally challenging profession.

The situation of crises is normal routine in the professional life of a nurse; therefore, inability to remain diligent and perseverant may affect the performance & job satisfaction of the nurses hence, the researcher felt a strong need to explore job satisfaction.

These results demonstrate The demographic factors studied in this research, such as age, marital status, educational attainment, and work experience, all have a positive relationship with job satisfaction.

Keywords: Job, satisfaction, Job Satisfaction, crises, educational attainment, work experience.

Cite as:

INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction is “the one’s feeling toward his/ her job. In which intrinsic and extrinsic factors influence job satisfaction”. Intrinsic factors are an internal willingness to perform duty with satisfaction and internal motives. External factor is the organization provides fridge benefits to the committed professional. However, these include the mixture of money, good scoring, and other rewards. (Forson et al., 2021).

Nursing is the most gratifying, demanding and emotionally challenging profession. Job satisfaction is identified by Spector (2021) as “the feeling of nurses about their profession, which may be positive and negative. He suggested that satisfied nurses are more effective at workplace that can minimize turnover intention”. Moreover, Mayer et al. (2011) justified that there is significant relationship between effective commitment and job satisfaction. Additionally, some researcher identified that there is inverse correlation between work stress environment and level of job satisfaction. (Joiner & Bartram, 2004). So the management is responsible to offer a healthy workplace to reserve nurse’s commitment towards an organization.

Empirical literature stated that organizational and individual factors affect the job satisfaction of the nurses that are huge workloads, insufficient staff and excessive regulation along with long working hours, bullying and rude behavior of the colleagues disrespectful public behavior and lazy unprofessional team members, continue rotation, living away from the home town, patients with more demanding leads to the nurses job dissatisfaction (Sener E.T;2002; Kaya and Bilgin, 2015).

The Research Problem

The situation of crises is normal routine in the professional life of a nurse; therefore, inability to remain diligent and perseverant may affect the performance & job satisfaction of the nurses hence, the researcher felt a strong need to explore job satisfaction.

In Pakistan, no earlier studies observed on job satisfaction level among nurses at the health care organization. Therefore, there was a dire need to study and observe

Objective of the research study

- To assess the job satisfaction among nurses at tertiary care hospital.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design:

A descriptive study design was used.

Study Subject:

It was selected from three tertiary care hospital of Punjab. 120 nurses participated through non-probability convenient sampling technique;

Study Too

Data is collected by using structured self-administered questionnaire. First part was the socio-demographic information of the participants. There were 21 questions in the questionnaires for checking the job satisfaction of the nurses.

Data Analysis:

Data is analyzed by SPSS version-20. To summarize the results, frequencies, percentages and table are used.

Demographic Variables Analysis

Table 3.1: Frequency Distribution of Hospital

Hospital	Frequency	Percent
Jinnah Hospital Lahore	40	33.3
Services Hospital Lahore	40	33.3
Holy Family Hospital	40	33.3
Total	120	100.0

According to Table No 3.1, Participants were chosen from Jinnah Hospital, Services Hospital, Lahore and Holy Family Hospital Rawalpindi, as shown in Table 4.4. 40 (33.3%) individuals were chosen from each facility.

Table 4.7: Frequency Distribution of Job Satisfaction Level

Job Satisfaction Level	Frequency	Percent
<20% (Very dissatisfied)	0	0.0
20–39% (Dissatisfied)	0	0.0
40–59% (Somewhat Satisfied)	6	5.0
60–79% (Satisfied)	114	95.0
80–100% (Strong Satisfied)	0	0.0
Total	120	100.0

Table 4.7, Job Satisfaction Levels, shows that the majority of participants, 114 (95.11%), were satisfied with their jobs, although only 6 (5.0%) were only somewhat satisfied. No person expressed being extremely satisfied or significantly disappointed.

The following pre-selected criteria were used to calculate it based on the achieved score in the job satisfaction level questions.

- If, 80 – 100% correct answers: Strong Satisfied
- If, 60 – 79% correct answers: Satisfied
- If, 40 – 59% correct answers: Somewhat Satisfied
- If, 20 – 39%: correct answers: Dissatisfied
- If, Below 20% correct answers: Very dissatisfied

DISCUSSIONS

In this study first part of the research questionnaires were about the demographic information. 120 nurses participated from three tertiary care hospitals. One hospital is from Rawalpindi, while two are from Lahore. The mean age of the nurses was 29.48 ± 2.17 years. A large number of nurses (71 out of 120) were from age group above 32 years. Majority of the nurses (62.5%) nurses were married. More than half of the nurses (61.7%) had more than 6 years of the professional experience. A reasonable number (42.5%) of the nurses were specialized.

According to the current study's analysis of work satisfaction levels, 114 (95.11%) of the participants were satisfied with their jobs (table 4.7). No individual expressed being extremely unsatisfied, dissatisfied, or strongly satisfied with their job. Similar to our results, several studies have found a relatively high job satisfaction level among nurses. (Sharp, 2008; Castle, 2006; Kacel et al., 2005; Sibbald et al., 2000). While a low level of job satisfaction was observed among nurses in many studies. (Bodur, 2002; Curtis, 2007; Vranes et al 2008; Hwang et al., 2009; Miller et al 2005)

According to Upreti, P.P.'s (2008) study, most participants (78%) expressed average satisfied, 21% expressed dissatisfaction, and only 1% was determined to be extremely satisfied. Researchers Sathyajith S. and Dr. R. Haridas conducted a study to assess the job satisfaction of nurses in Kerala hospitals (2013). It was shown that 144 nurses (72%) reported a moderate level of job satisfaction, while only 26 nurses (13%) reported a low level of job satisfaction. The fact that job satisfaction is difficult to measure objectively because it is influenced by a variety of factors, including the current social, economic, and working conditions and conditions that vary between studies, is one explanation for these discrepancies. Personal characteristics also play a role in defining job satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

These results demonstrate The demographic factors studied in this research, such as age, marital status, educational attainment, and work experience, all have a positive relationship with job satisfaction. The results highlighted that increase in nurse's job satisfaction, will turn improves nursing care quality.

Following a review of the relevant literature, it was found that nurses who exhibit technical skills as well as certain personal qualities like self-assured, empathic, observant, compassionate, participatory, visionary, and receptive reported high level of job satisfaction. Similarly, by resolving the issue associated to the clinical environment, job satisfaction could be maintained or increased..

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